

Domestic Violence and the Health of Women in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract

The study analyzed domestic violence and the health of women in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. Four research objectives were used to guide the study. The radical feminist theory was used. The research design used was a method design involving the administration of questionnaire and oral interview. 150 respondents mainly women who had experienced domestic violence or currently in such a relationship were sampled. The cluster sampling technique was used. Two women were orally interviewed to provide in-depth information on the subject. Findings revealed that domestic violence is prevalent in Obio-Akpor, and the results showed that 55(37%) of the respondents strongly agreed that jealousy problems cause domestic violence, 56(37%) respondents strongly agreed that suspicion of infidelity is a cause of domestic violence, 45(30%) respondents strongly agreed that economic dependence on partners causes domestic violence, Furthermore, 60(40%) respondents also strongly agreed that that verbal third party interference is a cause of domestic violence, while 57(38%) respondents strongly agreed that lack of trust causes domestic violence. Finally, 63(42%) respondents strongly agreed that kicking out of anger is a cause of domestic violence. Also some that have experienced intimate partner violence experienced internal and external health problems such as physical injuries, high blood pressure, chronic pain, insomnia, anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, isolation, and suicidal tendencies. The study recommends that women experiencing domestic violence should report to the authorities, seek counselling and psychosocial support, and if that proves abortive and the situation becomes life threatening, they can leave such relationship for health and life sakes.

Keywords: Domestic Violence, Women, Health, Obio-Akpor, Rivers State.

Introduction

Throughout the globe, attacks against women have been acknowledged as a malaise, permeating cultural, regional, religious, socio-economic boundaries (Orji, 2016). Generally, women have suffered severely from medical problems, such as chronic and acute physical injuries, loss of hearing or vision, miscarriage, depression, physical disfigurement, pelvic pain, anxiety, cardiovascular problems, bruises, broken bones among others. The reason for these complex problems may in many cases be traced to domestic violence, due to women economic dependence on men, especially, in Nigeria where patriarchy system and the differential socialization practice is high. Domestic violence can be felt in several forms such as girlfriend/spouse abuse, maltreatment, torture, forced commercial sex work, trafficking, etc (Human Rights Dialogue, 2017). Attacks against women can be regarded as the most pervasive type of maltreatment, a global malaise that cuts across class divisions, ethnic affiliations, region, religious beliefs (Omand, 2018). The usual form of domestic violence is found within the home, where many men maltreat or abuse their wives/girlfriends/fiancées (Watkins, 2019). The predominance of domestic violence has a serious effect on the biological, mental and social demeanour of many women, both young and old, and this is a profound cause of disastrous outcomes for women (WHO, 2017). A large number of the female sex are wounded bruised and murdered yearly due to the domestic violence (Hart, 2016). Domestic violence is not just a pioneering factor for concern to general health but is a direct and invariably a form of abuse on women that is not welcomed (Nwankwo, 2017).

According to World Health, domestic violence has permeated society and is not a malaise but given cultural excuses, especially, as it seen as a way of flexing the male muscles and superiority, victims of domestic violence are afraid to speak up for fear of stigmatization and public backlash. In addition, many media houses do not report domestic violence constantly, since many are interested in commercials and other programmes that will help foot their ever-increasing expenditure (WHO, 2016).

Famakinwa (2016) opined that the Nigeria Police Force could do more in the prevention and management of domestic violence. When matters of domestic violence reach police stations, most of these police officers throw out the complaints of the female victims, citing such matters as internal family issues that must be settled with the family or relationship. In addition, many Human Rights Organizations, Non-Governmental Organizations have been active in the fight against the increasing domestic violence but more is needed to be done. The insufficient fight against this scourge has made it, especially against women, a serious cause for concern, locally and globally. The women in Nigeria are prone/vulnerable to abusive and violent attacks, especially the uneducated ones in the rural and urban areas from their partners since they are seen as second fiddle or inferior to their partners. As a result of these, women are exposed to various health consequences due to domestic violence. To this end, one of the sustainable development Goals

(SDG 5) is dedicated to achieving gender equality and empower all women and girls, especially in developing countries found in Africa (Nweke, 2017). Domestic violence is a style of aggressive attitude in any friendship employed by a partner to have an upper hand unduly and dictate things to the other domestic. Domestic violence is seen also as an attack at home where the female spouse suffer beatings, kicking, battering from her husband. It is a style of aggressive behavior that is growing unabated and many young men are growing up to believe this is the norm in order to keep the females in check. Sadly, some fathers teach their boys how to be masculine physically so as to get fear out of the women. The cultural settings of the Nigeria society are creating daily room for the perpetuation of domestic violence on the women (Oviedo, 2017).

Aim and Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the meaning of domestic violence in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area.
2. To investigate the causes of domestic violence in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area.

Research Questions

1. What is the meaning of domestic violence in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area?
1. What are the causes of domestic violence in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area?

Significance of the Study

This study is vital because it will put forward the experiences many women go through in the hands of their partners. Domestic violence is one patriarchal horror that has perpetuated for years without proper check from authorities. So, this study will seek to enlighten readers on the dangers it has for female victims. The study will also contribute to matters relating to gender studies, especially in areas of inequality.

Scope of the Study

The scope of this study is Obio-Akpor Local Government Area, which has over 17 communities, out of which married and single women and men will be used as the key focus group by the researcher.

Definition of Terms

Domestic: Either member of a married couple or of an established unmarried couple that are closely acquainted or familiar. This can also be cohabiting partners, dating partners, courting partners, or partners that are engaged.

Violence: Behaviour involving physical force intended to hurt, damage, or kill someone or something.

Health Status: A condition of complete physical, mental, and social wellbeing.

Wellbeing: The state of being comfortable, healthy or happy.

Domestic Violence: A pattern or behaviour in any relationship that is used to gain or maintain power and control over an intimate partner.

Concept of Domestic Violence

Domestic violence is the intentional and persistent abuse of anyone in the home in a way that causes pain, distress or injury. It refers to any abusive treatment of one family member by another, thus violating the law of basic human rights. It includes battering of domestics and others, sexual abuse of children, marital rape and traditional practices that are harmful to women. Domestic violence occurs globally (Dahlberg and Krug, 2016, UNICEF, 2018). Families from all social, racial economic, educational and religious backgrounds experience domestic violence in different ways. Djaden and Thoennes (2016), report that in the United States of America, each year, women experience about 4.8 million domestic-related physical assaults and rapes while men are victims of about 2.9 million domestic related physical assaults. In parts of the third world generally and in West Africa, in particular, domestic violence is prevalent and reportedly justified and condoned in some cultures. For instance, 56% of Senegalese women surveyed by an agency justified wife-beating on grounds like –bad cook, disrespectful to in-laws, producing more girls, leaving home without informing, among others (Basu and Pratishtan, 2018). In Nigeria, reports reveal “shockingly high” level of violence against women. Amnesty International (2020) reported that a third (and in some cases two-thirds) of women are believed to have been subjected to physical, sexual and psychological violence carried out primarily by husbands, partners and fathers while girls are often forced into early marriage and are at risk of punishment if they attempt to escape from their husbands. More pathetic is the revelation of gross under reporting and non documentation of domestic violence due to cultural factors (Oyediran and Isugo, 2016). Traditionally, in Nigeria, as in many other African countries, the beating of wives and children is widely sanctioned as a form of discipline (UNICEF, 2016). Therefore, in beating their children parents believe they are instilling discipline in them, much the same way as in husbands beating their wives, who are regarded like children to be prone to indiscipline which must be curbed.

This is especially so when the woman is economically dependent on the man. The society is basically patriarchal and women’s place within the scheme is decidedly subordinate. Domestic violence therefore functions as a means of enforcing conformity with the role of a woman within customary society. It therefore does not matter if the woman is economically dependent or not, her position, like that of the children is subordinate. Violence against women in the home is generally regarded as belonging to the private sphere in Nigeria and is therefore shielded from outside scrutiny. A culture of silence reinforces the stigma attached to the victim rather than condemning the perpetrator of such crimes (Bashins, 2018). Ademola (2019), in a survey on violence against women conducted interviews with women working in the markets and other places of work and

girls and young women in secondary schools and universities, in Lagos State, Nigeria. 64.4% of 45 women interviewed in the work place said they had been beaten by their partners (boyfriends or husbands), 56.6% of 48 interviewed market woman admitted experiencing such violence. Similar interviews carried out in Oyo State and other parts of Nigeria, yielded similar results. The incidence of domestic violence is high. In a study, carried out by Obi and Ozumba (2016), on the factors associated with domestic violence in South East, Nigeria, 70% of respondents reported abuse in their family with 92% of the victims being female partners and the remaining 8% being male. The common forms of abuse reported were shouting at a partner (93%), slapping or pushing (77%) and punching and kicking (40%). It is however disturbing to note that many women do not know if they had been abused or not (Olanikan, 2017). This could be due to the acceptance of some abusive behaviour as 'normal'. Obapitan (2015), in a study of women's perception of wife-beating in Nigeria found that 64.4% and 50.4% of married and unmarried women, respectively, expressed consent for wife beating. Reports in the print and electronic media reveal vicious attacks on women by domestic violence in different forms such as 'acid bath', rape, beatings, some of which sometimes result in the death of the victim. Many victims do not report for fear of reprisal from abusers or the belief that the police and the judicial system cannot help. The police are also reported to frequently dismiss complaints of domestic violence as a 'private matter'.

Forms of Domestic Violence

Physical Abuse

Physical abuse is an abuse involving contact intended to cause feelings of pain, injury, intimidation, physical suffering or bodily harm punching, hitting, pushing and many other kind of body contact that result to physical injuries. For Obilade (2016), physical violence employs brute force against an individual in a manner that gives the individual a serious wound/injury. It is the simplest form of behaviour to be seen and called violence.

Emotional Violence/Abuse

Emotional violence can be regarded as psychological abuse or mental abuse and can be informed of verbal or non-verbal abuse. This form of violence includes isolating the victim from socializing or associating with friends and family, harassing or humiliating the victim publicly or privately, controlling the victim on what to do or not and deliberately provoking the victim to anger or to make the victim feel diminished and embarrassed (National Coalition against Domestic, 2019).

Sexual Violence and Marital Rape

Sexual violence is any situation in which force or threat is applied to obtain participation in unwanted sexual activity. Sexual abuse usually resulted to physical violence by forcing someone to engage in a sexual activity (Bealett, 2015). Abayo (2017) see sexual abuse as an attempt to

obtain sexual act, unwanted sexual comment or advances or acts to traffic or otherwise directed against a person's sexuality using force regardless of their relationship. Marital rape on the other hand is the use of force to compel a person to engage in a sexual act against one's will. Marital rape occurs when a partner takes part in sexual act without the victim's consent (Obike, 2016).

Economic Violence

Economic violence is a form of violence when one domestic has control over the other partner's access to economic resources. Many studies have reviewed that majority of the perpetrators of this abuse are men especially in most developing countries like Nigeria. Economic abuse may involve preventing a partner or spouse from using resources or by exploiting economic resources of the victim (Brewster, 2016). The reason behind men preventing women who are their spouses from acquiring resources is to reduce women's capacity to support themselves and ensure they totally depend on the men for survival financially and prevent the women from finding employment, preventing the women from advancing their careers and acquiring assets. These results to control and abuse of women right (Adeniran, 2018).

Verbal Violence

Verbal abuse is referred to the use of language to control or subordinate another person for either self-gratification or to impose ones will or view on another person or to gain an unfair advantage in resolving a dispute (Olsen, 2018).

Causes of Domestic Violence

There are many different causes of domestic violence.

- 1 **Psychological:** Psychological scholars focus on personality traits and mental characteristics of the offender. Personal traits include sudden bursts of anger, poor impulse control and poor self-esteem. Various scholars suggest that psychopathology and other personality disorders are factors, and that abuse observed or experienced as a child lead some people to be more violent in adulthood (Obi, 2016). Dutton & Golant (2015) suggested a psychological profile of men who abuse their wives, arguing that they have borderline personalities that are developed early in life.
- 2 **Jealousy:** Many cases of domestic violence against women occur due to jealousy when the spouse is either suspected of being unfaithful or is planning to leave the relationship. An evolutionary psychology explanation of such cases of domestic violence against women is that they present to the male attempts to control female reproduction and ensure sexual exclusivity for himself through violence or the threat of violence (Goetz, 2016).
- 3 **Social Stress:** Stress may be increased when a person is living in a family situation, with increased pressures. Violence is not always caused by stress, but may be one way that some people respond to stress (Seltzer & Kalmuss, 2018). Couples in poverty may be more likely to experience domestic violence, due to increased stress and conflicts about finances and other aspects (Jewkes, 2016).

- 4 **Social Learning:** If one observes violent behaviour, one is more likely to imitate it. If there are no negative consequences and the victim also accepts the violence with submission; then the behaviour will likely continue. Often, violence is transmitted from generation to generation in a cyclical manner (Crowell & Sugarman, 2017).
- 5 **Power and Control:** Abusers abuse in order to establish and maintain control over the partner. Abusers effort to dominate have been attributed to low self-esteem or feelings of inadequacy, unresolved childhood conflicts, the stress of poverty, hostility and resentment toward women (misogyny), personality disorders, genetic tendencies and social cultural influences (Alaro, 2018). Most authorities seem to agree that abusive personalities result from a combination of several factors to varying degrees.

Social Works and Domestic Violence

Over the years, social workers have adopted means of preventing domestic violence around Nigeria. They believed it is safer to prevent the scourge than treating patients. This is why they used three preventive processes. There is three prevention process of violence, primary, secondary and tertiary prevention. Primary prevention is reducing the number of new instances of intimate partner violence or sexual violence by intervening before any violence occurs. Primary prevention of domestic violence is working towards changing the behaviours and belief of the society towards domestic violence and preventing it before it occurs to prevent initial perpetration. Primary intervention programs include dating violence prevention program which focuses on increasing domestic violence knowledge and working towards beliefs and behavioural change, media campaigns inform of radio spots, television and posters to create awareness of domestic violence. Secondary prevention is the response after the violence has occurred. This process helps to manage the short-term consequences and prevent future perpetration and victimization. Secondary intervention programs argues that couples counseling, substance abuse counseling, screening for domestic violence which involves social workers asking structured questions to determine if one has been victims of domestic violence are interventions to be taken when the violence has occurred in order to stop it from happening again. Community-based services for victims include transitional housing and advocacy (social and emotional support), police responses and prosecutorial and judicial responses (Williamson, 2019). Tertiary prevention of domestic violence is the long-term responses to domestic violence after violence has occurred. This process helps to deal with consequences of lasting violence and intervention treatment for both victims and perpetrator. Tertiary prevention of domestic violence includes counseling, a correctional facility for women and legal advocacy (Aderonke, 2019).

Research Methodology

A research design is the pattern the researcher intends to adopt in collecting and collating data. In this research work, a cross sectional design will be adopted. The design will be qualitative and quantitative. The qualitative will use interviews, while the quantitative will use questionnaires in collecting and collating data. Obio-Akpor Local Government Area is found in Rivers State. Obio-Akpor is the capital city of Rivers State. It shares boundary with Aluu, Emohua, Port Harcourt. Obio-Akpor has a long history of marital and relationship violence. In 2020, the Federation of International Women Lawyers (FIDA) reported over 400 cases of domestic violence between 2015 and 2019; an issue further heightened by the lockdown during the corona virus era in 2020. The area is an industrious one where men and women are into formal jobs, pushing aside the traditional roles of men and women to a larger extent, and these changes in the traditional roles of many women have become problematic for them, as many have suffered violent attacks and maltreatment from their spouses, lovers, etc. The population of the study included single and married men and women. The men are selected as part of the study because the researcher needed to draw the views of men as to why domestic violence is mostly perpetuated by men. It would be unjust to look from the angle of the women only. So, the men will form part of the respondents selected for the study. A sample is a smaller, manageable aspect of a larger group. It is a smaller, manageable aspect of a larger group. It is a subset considerate of the features of a bigger populace. The study will sample 180 respondents drawn from four localities in the study area: Alakahia, Choba, Rumuosi, Rumuekini. This means 45 respondents will be drawn from the four localities respectively. The population size of these localities put together is 72,000 according to the Rivers State Bureau of Statistics (2019). The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane was used.

Table 1: Sample Size Determination

Table with 2 columns: Taro Yamane and Population. It shows the calculation for sample size determination using the formula N = N / (1 + N(e)^2) where N = 72,000 and (e)^2 = 0.0025, resulting in a sample size of 180.

In addition, a sampling technique is the name or other identification of the specific process by which the entities of the sample have been selected. For this study, the cluster sampling technique will be used. This technique allows the researcher to make the entire population externally homogenous, but internally heterogeneous by divided it into groups. The researcher will sample

the views of both the single and married women that have been victims of domestic violence. To complement the cluster sampling technique, the simple random sampling technique will be used to enable the researcher randomly pick respondents since everyone cannot be involved in the study. Data used in this research work are got from questionnaires, interviews, articles, journals, the internet, etc. The questionnaire will be divided into parts. Part A will be on the personal features of respondents. Part B will be on the meaning of intimate violence. Part C will be on the causes of domestic violence. Part D will be on the views of respondents on the health implications of domestic violence. The questions will be open-ended and close-ended in structure. Additionally, the respondents will be interviewed by the researcher for more data on the study. Data collected was analysed in line with the research questions. Respondents' reactions to the questions posed was determined by the four likert scale of strongly agree, agree, strongly disagree, disagree. The views of respondents as regards domestic violence obtained via interviews was analysed as well.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Demographic Features of Respondents

Table with 3 columns: Items, No. of Respondents, Percentage (%). Rows include Sex (Male/Female), Age (18-25, 26-35, 36-45, 46-above), and Marital Status (Single/Married/Divorced).

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The data analysis for respondents' sex showed that 30(20%) were males, while 120(80%) were females. Based on the age of the respondents, the majority of them 70(47) were between 26 and 35 years, while 50(33%) were between 18 and 25, 20(13%) respondents were between 36 and 45 years, whereas 10(7%) were above 45 years.

Research Question One: What is the meaning of domestic violence?

Table 2: Responses on Meaning of Domestic Violence

Table with 6 columns: S/N, Item/Variables, SA, A, SD, D. Rows include items like 'Physical fights between two lovers', 'Hit or being threatened by a partner', etc.

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The above table address question on the meaning of domestic violence. To answer this question, the responses on items 1-4 of section "B" of the questionnaire were analyzed. 71(47%) of the total respondents strongly agreed to the view that domestic violence is seen in physical fights between two lovers, 43(29%) agreed, 20(13%) strongly disagreed, 16(11%) disagreed. Also, 64(43%) and 36(24%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that being hit or threatened by a partner is domestic violence, while 30(20%) and 20(13%) strongly disagreed and disagreed. 58(39%) of the respondents strongly agreed that being in an abusive relationship for long is domestic violence, 46(31%) agreed, 24(16%) strongly disagreed, while 22(15%) disagreed. 60(40%) respondents strongly agreed that intentional injury from an domestic is domestic violence, 48(32%) agreed, 20(13%) strongly disagreed while 22(15%) disagreed.

Research Question Two: What are the causes of domestic violence?

Table 3: Responses on causes of domestic violence.

Table with 6 columns: S/N, Item/Variable, SA, A, SD, D. Rows include items like 'Incompatibility of values', 'Suspicion of infidelity', 'Economic dependence on partner', etc.

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The second research question addresses the causes of domestic violence. The essence of this research question is to find out the causes of domestic violence in the research area. In item 5 of the table, 55(37) respondents strongly agreed that jealousy problems cause domestic violence, 43(29%) agreed, 27(18%) strongly disagreed while 23(15%) disagreed. Also, 56(37%) respondents strongly agreed that suspicion of infidelity is a cause of domestic violence, 48(32%) agreed. Meanwhile, 2(17%) and 21(14%) respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. In item 7 of the table, 45(30%) respondents strongly agreed that economic dependence on partners is a cause of domestic violence, 40(27%) agreed, 35(23%) strongly disagreed, while 30(20%) disagreed. Furthermore, 60(40%) respondents strongly agreed that verbal third party interference is a cause of domestic violence, 36(24%) agreed, 32(21%) strongly disagreed, while 22(15%) respondents disagreed. 57(38%) respondents strongly agreed that lack of trust is cause of domestic violence. Meanwhile, 61(41%) respondents agreed, 15(10%) strongly disagreed, 17(11%) disagreed. Finally, 63(42%) respondents strongly agreed that kicking out of anger is a cause of domestic violence. Meanwhile, 55(37%) respondents agreed, 18(12%) and 14(9%) strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively.

Discussion of Findings

In Nigeria, reports reveal “shockingly high” level of violence against women. Amnesty International (2020) reported that a third (and in some cases two-thirds) of women are believed to have been subjected to physical, sexual and psychological violence carried out primarily by husbands, partners and fathers while girls are often forced into early marriage and are at risk of punishment if they attempt to escape from their husbands. More pathetic is the revelation of gross under reporting and non documentation of domestic violence due to cultural factors (Oyediran and Isugo, 2016). Traditionally, in Nigeria, as in many other African countries, the beating of wives and children is widely sanctioned as a form of discipline (UNICEF, 2016). Result of research question one in table 2 shows that there are relationships suffering domestic violence. Majority of the respondents all agree that domestic violence is real and frequent. The result agrees with the submission of Osakwe (2013) that there are love affairs nowadays that are undergoing strain as a result of domestic violence in major cities in Africa and Nigeria particularly. Also, result from research question two revealed that there are causes of domestic violence in Obio-Akpor. Respondents indicate that their domestics have jealousy problems they have been forced to have sex with their partners, and other causes. This result is in tandem with the findings of Agbaji, Akhabue and Duruaku (2018) in their study of conflict within relationships stated that many affairs are suffering violence due to insecurities of men and women. Also, Allison (2019) asserts that many females are in abusive affairs due to the problem of personality that many men are suffering.

Recommendations

- i. Young women must take time to assess the men they intend to date, marry if they are emotionally, psychologically balanced.
2. Women that are in abusive relationships be it dating or marriage must learn to speak up before they are killed or injured permanently.

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